

HERBAL HAIR SERUM

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ABSTRACT

More & more people want personal care products that are natural & free from chemicals. This has led to the creation of a water based herbal hair serum made with carefully chosen plant ingredients that are known to be good for hair & scalp health. Alopecia is a common problem for people living in cities due to stress, pollution & other factors. This review paper suggests that herbal treatment can effectively treat hair loss without causing side effect. To boost hair growth & prevent hair loss, hair roots need activation. Sweet orange fights dandruff black seeds strengthens & adds shine, coconut oil keeps hair moisturized. The clinical study was designed to efficacy & safety of a hair serum formulation containing aloe extract, warm coconut oil in healthy male & female volunteers with hair fall.

KEYWORDS: Alopecia, coconut, dandruff, hair serum, shine.

INTRODUCTION

Hair is a complex structure with special chemical & physical properties. Hair care products are used to make it look better. Hair goes through a natural cycle where it grows, combines with other strands, get longer & eventually falls out. Natural or herbal cosmetic are products made from approved cosmetic ingredients along with one or more plant based ingredient. These herbal parts are added to give specific beauty benefit. Coconut oil give nourishes the scalp, reduces hair breakage & adds shine. aloe vera give soothe the scalps, reduces dandruff & moisturizes hair. Almond oil help with its hair nourishing & skin softening properties. vit e

help to strengthen hair improve scalp circulation & promote hair growth. Hair serum are light & easy to use products that help make hair smoother, easier to manage & protect it from damage caused by the environment. There are different types of hair serums for different hair goals.

Types Of Hair Serum

Based on formula

Based on therapeutic action

1) Aloe Vera

Aloe vera has been used for a long time to help with hair loss. It also calms the scalp, makes hair soft, reduces dandruff & clears blocked hair roots caused by extra oil. You can apply fresh aloe vera gel to your scalp & hair a few times a week when the skin get too much sun.

Synonym → Indian Aloe, Aloe barbadensis, kumari.

Family → Liliaceae / Asphodelaceae.

Biological Source → It consist of the mucilage obtained from the parenchymatus cell of the leaves of Aloe barbadensis Mill.

Part Used → Fresh leaves.

Chemical Constituents →

2) Almond Oil

1. Anthraquinones 2. Polysacharide 3. Vitamines 4. Enzyme

1. Minerals

Almond oil keep the scalp hydrated & makes hair strong, thick & shiny. Almond oil help reduce dandruff because it fights bacteria, heals dry skin & removes dead skin cells. Since it has biotin (Vit B), it is useful for people with thin hair as it helps hair grow & reduces hair fall. Almond oil also protects the skin from sun damage, slows ageing & guards cell by reducing harm from UV rays.

3) Vitamine E.

Vitamine E oil makes hair shiny again by fixing its natural cover. Oils is general keep the hair moist, stop it from breaking & protect it from damage. Vitamine E has natural antioxidants that may help hair grow & keep the scalp health.

These antioxidants also fight harmful thing that can weaken & damage hair roots.

4) Coconut Oil

Coconut oil is one of the best natural nutrients for hair. It helps hair shiny & healthy & prevents proteins loss which can cause weak or unhealthy hair. In india & nearby countries many people use coconut oil daily after a bath. It works like a good conditioner helps repair damage hair & provides important protein that make hair strong. Studies show that coconut oil

protect hair iron damage & regular head massages with it is very helpful.

5) Rose Water

Rose water gives moisture so your hair smooth & shiny doesn't feel dry or rough. It makes your hair smooth & shiny & helps control flyaways. Rose water help to control how oily/dry your scalp gets, keeping it healthy. Rose water has a soft sweet smell that makes your hair feel.

Formulation

➤ *Extract the Aloe Gel* →

Cut & wash the aloe vera leaf then remove the rind & the thorny sides get the fresh gel.

➤ *Blend the gel* →

Transfer the gel into a blender (chutney grinder) & blend until it smooth & free of lumps.

➤ *Add other Ingredients* →

Add 2 tablespoons of coconut oil Squeeze the contents of 2 vit. E capsules into the mixture add 3 tablespoons of almond oil Optionally, add 2 tablespoons of rosewater

➤ *Stir well* →

Mix all the ingredients thoroughly until you have a uniform serum.

➤ *Store the serum* →

Transfer the serum into a bottle with a dropper & store it in the refrigerator for 3–5 days for best result.

Formulation Table

Ingredient	Quantity (%)	Role
Coconut Oil	10	Detangles hair
Aloe vera	20	Hydrates scalp
Almond oil	15	Hair growth
Vitamin E	2	Healthy scalp
Rose water	10	Natural fragrance

CONCLUSION

The herbal hair serum has been successfully formulated. These natural formulation offer a promising, safe, effective alternative to synthetic products for enhancing hair health & growth. All ingredient added have many advantages such as maintaining good growth of hair, protecting damage from the environment, keep hair healthy, stop it from looking dry & make it smooth & shiny, reduced risk of side effects. Humans days are now really interested in herbs because of strength.

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